

Chromones and Flavones. Part V*. Synthesis of Some 3',3'''- and 6,6''-Biflavonyls

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The bichalkonyl derivatives, obtained from the condensation of 2,2'- and 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diformylbiphenyls with 2-hydroxyacetophenone and from the condensation of 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl with benzaldehyde, have been converted into the corresponding biflavonyl derivatives. Some of these have also been obtained by the Ullmann reaction on the appropriate iodoflavones. The Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation of 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl has been studied. Some of the chalcones have been isomerised to the flavanones.

Several biflavonyls have been synthesised so far in low yields through either a simple or crossed Ullmann reaction on the appropriate iodoflavones¹⁻⁵. It was thought of interest to ascertain the possibility of synthesising biflavonyls by building up the pyrone rings simultaneously on suitable biphenyl derivatives. The present work deals with the synthesis of some 3',3'''- and 6,6''-biflavonyls by this new approach.

4,4'-Dimethoxy-3,3'-diformylbiphenyl⁶ on condensation with 2-hydroxyacetophenone in presence of EtOH-KOH furnished the bichalkonyl derivative (Ia), which developed a red colour with H₂SO₄ (conc.), a faint brown colour with ethanolic ferric chloride⁷, responded to a positive Wilson test⁷, and formed a diacetyl derivative. On refluxing with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol, it afforded the 3',3'''-biflavonyl derivative (IIa), which was also obtained by an alternative synthesis, as follows:

2-Hydroxyacetophenone was condensed with 2-methoxy-5-iodobenzaldehyde in presence of EtOH-KOH. The product obtained was 2-hydroxy-2'-methoxy-5-iodochalkone as it responded to positive tests for a chalcone and formed a monoacetyl derivative. When refluxed with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol, it provided 2'-methoxy-5'-iodoflavone, which on being subjected to the Ullmann reaction afforded a product, identical with the biflavonyl derivative, described above. The iodochalkone was also isomerised to 2'-methoxy-5'-iodoflavanone by refluxing with EtOH-HCl.

Similarly as above, 2,2'-dimethoxy-5,5'-diformylbiphenyl⁶ provided the bichalkonyl derivative (Ib), which with selenium dioxide furnished the biflavonyl (IIb). This was also

*Part IV. Shah and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 507.

1. Chen and Liu, *J. Taiwan Pharm. Soc.*, 1953, 5, 53; *Chem. Abst.*, 1955, 49, 5464.

2. Chen *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 232.

3. Jurd, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 322.

4. Shah, *Curr. Sci.*, 1962, 31, 57.

5. Nakazawa and Ito, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Tokyo*, 1963, 11, 283.

6. Mathai and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 347.

7. Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2303.

†Faint colour is probably due to the very sparing solubility of the bichalkonyl in ethanol.

obtained by the Ullmann reaction on 4'-methoxy-3'-iodoflavone, prepared from 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-iodochalkone, which in turn was obtained by the condensation of 2-hydroxyacetophenone with 4-methoxy-3-iodobenzaldehyde. 2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-iodochalkone was also isomerised to 4'-methoxy-3'-iodoflavanone.

(For I & II. a: R = OMe; R' = H. b: R = H; R' = OMe)

(a: R = H. b: R = C(=O)Ph)

Condensation of 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbiophenyl⁸ with benzaldehyde similarly yielded 6,6''-dihydroxy-3',3'''-bichalkonyl derivative, which on refluxing with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol provided 6,6''-biflavonyl (IIIa). This was also obtained when 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbiophenyl was subjected to the Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation at 210-15° and the dibenzoyl derivative (IIIb) obtained was hydrolysed with 2% ethanolic NaOH. 6',6'''-Dihydroxy-3',3'''-bichalkonyl was isomerised to 6,6''-biflavanonyl by refluxing in ethanolic HCl for 30 hr.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Chalkones and Bichalkonyls.—To a mixture of the hydroxyketone and aldehyde (0.01M or 0.02M of each as required), dissolved in ethanol, KOH (10 g. in 10 ml water) was added and the mixture was kept for 24 hr. in a well-stoppered flask. It was then diluted and acidified with HCl. The precipitated chalkone derivative was crystallised from ethanol-acetone mixture and the bichalkonyl derivative from nitrobenzene. All the bichal-

8. Stoughton *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2007.

*All melting points are uncorrected.

konyls prepared in this work were found to be insoluble in ether, benzene, and acetone but soluble in nitrobenzene (Table I).

TABLE I
Chalkones and bichalkonyls.

No.	Compound.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	2',2'''-Dihydroxy-6,6''-dimethoxy-3,3''-bichalkonyl(Ia)	264°	50 %	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₆	C : 75.9 % H : 5.0	75.9 % 5.1
2.	2',2'''-Dihydroxy-4,4''-dimethoxy-3,3''-bichalkonyl(Ib)	260°	59	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ O ₆	C : 75.6 H : 5.4	75.9 5.1
3.	6',6'''-Dihydroxy-3',3'''-bichalkonyl(Ic)	202°	66	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	C : 81.0 H : 4.9	80.7 4.9
4.	2'-Hydroxy-2-methoxy-5-iodochalkone	135°	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ I	C : 50.5 H : 2.9 I : 33.6	50.5 3.4 33.4
5.	2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-iodochalkone	169°	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ I	C : 50.4 H : 3.4 I : 33.3	50.5 3.4 33.4

TABLE II
Acetyl derivatives of chalkones and bichalkonyls (vide Table I).

No.	Compound.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
2.	2',2'''-Diacetoxy-	95°	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ O ₈	C : 73.1 % H : 5.2	73.2 % 5.1
3.	6',6'''-Diacetoxy-	112°	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₆	C : 76.5 H : 4.8	76.9 4.9
4.	2'-Acetoxy-	94°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ I	C : 51.1 H : 3.2 I : 30.5	51.2 3.6 30.1
5.	2'-Acetoxy-	129°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₄ I	C : 51.4 H : 3.7 I : 30.2	51.2 3.6 30.1

Flavones and Biflavanonyls.—The chalkone or bichalkonyl derivative was refluxed in sufficient ethanol containing HCl (conc.) for 30 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation, the resulting mixture was diluted with water, and the precipitated flavanone derivative was crystallised from acetic acid or benzene. The flavanones are colorless or slightly coloured compounds, soluble in acetone and ethanol, develop a yellow or orange colour with H₂SO₄ (conc.) and do not respond to EtOH-FeCl₃ colour reaction. Characteristics and analytical data of the compounds are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Compound.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
3.	6,6''-Biflavanonyl	252°	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	C : 81.1 % H : 4.8	80.7 % 4.9
4.	2'-Methoxy-5'-iodoflavanone*	138°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ I	C : 50.4 H : 3.7 I : 33.7	50.5 3.4 33.4
5.	4'-Methoxy-3'-iodoflavanone*	100°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ I	C : 50.5 H : 3.2 I : 33.2	50.5 3.4 33.4

*Mixed m. p. with isomeric chalkones was depressed by more than 10°.

Flavones and Biflavonyls.—The chalkone or bichalkonyl derivative was refluxed with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol at 140-50° in an oil bath for 15 hr. It was filtered hot. The flavone or biflavonyl derivative separated either on cooling or on removal of the solvent by steam distillation. The flavones were crystallised from toluene and the biflavonyls from diphenyl ether. The biflavonyls obtained in the present work are light coloured compounds and sparingly soluble in common organic solvents (Table IV).

TABLE IV

No.	Compounds.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	6',6'''-Dimethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl (IIa)	271°	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₆	C : 76.2 % H : 4.3	76.6 % 4.4
2.	4',4'''-Dimethoxy-3',3'''-biflavonyl (IIb)	327°	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ O ₆	C : 76.2 H : 4.7	76.5 4.4
3.	6,6''-Biflavonyl(IIc)*	307°	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ O ₄	C : 81.1 H : 4.3	81.5 4.1
4.	2'-Methoxy-5'-iodoflavone	137°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ I	C : 50.4 H : 2.6 I : 33.5	50.8 2.9 33.6
5.	4'-Methoxy-3'-iodoflavone*	192°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ I	C : 50.7 H : 2.9 I : 33.6	50.8 2.9 33.6

*Chen *et al.*², who prepared the same biflavonyl by a different method, reported m.p. 305-307°.

†Jurd³, who prepared the same compound by another method, reported m.p. 193°.

Acetyl Derivatives.—The chalkone or bichalkonyl derivative was refluxed with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate in an oil bath at 140-50° for 2 hr. The acetyl derivative (Table II) separating on pouring the reaction mixture in water was crystallised from acetic acid or benzene.

Ullmann Reaction.—The iodoflavone was mixed with an equal amount of copper bronze and heated at 250-60° in an oil bath for 2 hr. Alternatively, the mixture was refluxed in diphenyl ether for 2 hr. In the former case, the mixture was extracted with nitrobenzene. On removal of the solvent by steam distillation and working up as usual, the biflavonyl was obtained in both the cases.

2',2'''-6,6'''-Tetramethoxy-3,3'''-bichalkonyl was prepared by refluxing a mixture of bichalkonyl derivative (Ia, 1g.), dimethyl sulphate (1ml), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) in dry acetone for 6 hr. The product crystallised from benzene in light yellow needles, m.p. 217°. (Found: C 76.0; H, 5.5. C₃₄H₃₀O₆ requires C, 76.4; H, 5.6%).

3,3'''-Dibenzoyl-6,6''-biflavonyl.—A mixture of 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl biphenyl (1g.) sodium benzoate (4g.), and benzoic anhydride (12 g.) was heated at 210-15° in an oil bath for 10 hr. It was cooled, washed with sodium bicarbonate, and crystallised from nitrobenzene in white needles (1g.), m.p. 335°. (Found: C, 80.4; H, 3.7. C₄₄H₂₆O₆ requires C, 80.9; H, 4.0%). When the temperature was kept at 180-90°, only the *O*-benzoyl derivative was obtained.

The above biflavonyl was refluxed with 2% EtOH-NaOH over a steam bath for 2 hr. The residue after filtration and repeated crystallisations from nitrobenzene provided pure

6,6''-biflavonyl, identical with the one obtained by refluxing 6',6'''-dihydroxy-3',3'''-bichalkonyl with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol.

*5-Iodosalicylaldehyde*⁹.—Iodine monochloride (0.01 *M*, 1.63 g.) was slowly added to salicylaldehyde (0.01 *M*, 1.2 g.) at 25-30° with stirring. The reaction mixture after keeping overnight was poured on water. The product obtained furnished colorless needles from benzene-petroleum mixture, m.p. 102°. (Found: I, 51.2. C₇H₅O₂I requires I, 51.2%). Its structure was established by converting it into the known 4,4'-dimethoxy-3,3'-diformyl-biphenyl⁶ by methylation and Ullman reaction.

One of the authors (K.P.M.) thanks the Govt. of India for the award of a research training scholarship.

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Received March 7, 1964.

9. Visset, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1907, 235, 556, who prepared the same compound by a different method, reported the same m.p.